

Title: Recommendations for better cohort design for diagnostic research using electronic health records

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Diagnostic research involves understanding risk of as-yet undiagnosed disease in patients presenting with potential features of disease, and is key to improving diagnosis. Electronic health records offer unparalleled opportunities to quantify this risk. Yet, designing studies and sampling cohorts of patients with potential signs and symptoms in electronic health records can be challenging. Drawing on our experience examining risk of cancer and related diseases, we offer a series of actionable recommendations in addressing both general practical challenges and complex conceptual challenges inherent in using electronic health records to construct study cohorts for diagnostic research. We offer a broad framework within which researchers can situate a clear diagnostic research question, which can guide these difficult conceptual decisions.

Summary points

Diagnostic research aims to assess the short-term risk of present but as-yet undetected disease in patients with features that may indicate presence of disease, such as symptoms or abnormal test results. Electronic health record data are increasingly used to conduct these studies. We provide recommendations on handling the various challenges inherent in such research, drawing on our experience in predicting risk of cancer and related diseases.

Practical challenges arise from the nature of electronic health record data and are applicable to a wide range of observational studies, including diagnostic research. These include challenges with censoring and loss-to-follow-up from patients moving between data providers, defining (phenotyping) clinical states of interest, and selectively recorded data items.

Conceptual challenges also apply specifically to using electronic health records in retrospective cohort studies, where we must design cohorts of patients with prodromal features. These primarily arise from the difficulty of identifying exposures and selecting index dates in large-scale longitudinal data where completeness of recording may be in doubt.

Finally, we reflect on the recurring challenge of ensuring the dataset design can support appropriate analysis to answer the research questions, and summarise three relevant cohort designs for diagnostic research.

Introduction

One strand of epidemiological research aims to estimate the short-term risk of present but as-yet undetected disease in patients with potential prodromal features. We term this ‘diagnostic research’, to highlight differences from the well-established, but related, area of prognostic research, which identifies groups at high long-term risk of developing *future* disease.¹ The focus of ‘diagnostic research’ is on estimating short-term risk of underlying disease – usually within a few months or years after presentation with a potential feature, depending on the disease. This can inform doctors making decisions about which diagnoses and investigation strategies to consider in patients presenting with new-onset signs and symptoms, and has been used to support the development of diagnostic guidelines² and diagnostic tools.³

Electronic health records are increasingly used in both diagnostic and prognostic research, which historically required resource-intensive studies of large, prospective cohorts followed up over many years.⁴ Yet electronic health records are typically intended either for billing purposes or direct patient care – and so present unique challenges when used in research.⁴

Prognostic research studies have an existing framework;¹ as do reporting guidelines for electronic health record-based observational studies (RECORD – cohort checklist)⁵ and diagnostic prediction models.⁶ However, there is no broad guidance supporting observational electronic health record-based diagnostic research, particularly regarding study design and preparation of analysis datasets.

In this paper, which is intended as a guide, we draw on our experience in assessing risk of cancer and other diseases in patients with potential prodromal signs and symptoms. We provide a series of actionable recommendations. These recommendations relate to practical challenges arising from the nature of electronic health records, which are applicable to a wide range of observational studies including diagnostic research.⁷ We additionally discuss conceptual challenges in designing cohorts with potential prodromal features using such data. We finish with a framework of the three key diagnostic research types, arguing that better understanding is needed among researchers about which accompanying cohort designs are most appropriate.

Practical challenges in processing electronic health records data

Producing a clean analytical dataset from electronic health record databases presents challenges, as electronic health records are typically sourced from software systems used by healthcare providers for billing or the direct care of patients, and are not originally intended for research. We summarise the strengths and limitations of using electronic health records in Box 1. We discuss three of these problems in detail in this section: identifying outcomes and exposures, mitigating selective recording of clinical features, and dealing with censoring and competing risks.

Identifying outcomes and exposures ('phenotyping')

Electronic health records datasets are not designed for research use, so exposures (e.g. symptoms, signs) and outcomes (e.g. disease diagnosis) must be defined using phenotyping algorithms – sets of rules for combining concepts from medical ontologies (e.g. SNOMED concepts) or classification systems (e.g. ICD-10 terms), or strings of text that indicate whether a patient has or has not got a relevant feature.

Developing phenotyping algorithms in electronic health record data is challenging, in part because there is no single definition for each entity that can meet every study's aims. This is one reason for the proliferation of multiple code lists for the same conditions in the same ontology; for example, the HDR UK National Phenotype Library includes 12 different heart failure phenotypes defined using the Read version 2 ontology (<https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes>, search for "heart failure" conducted on 24/03/2025).

Often, a simple list of codes (e.g. SNOMED-CT concept IDs, or ICD-10 codes) is not sufficient to accurately identify patients with the event of interest. The accompanying patient-level inclusion and exclusion criteria and implementation logic must also be developed and made publicly available. For example, identifying surgical resections aimed at curing cancer requires consideration of the cancer site, stage of disease, the exact surgical procedure and its timing post-diagnosis, to distinguish this type of surgery from other surgical activity.⁸

Two key challenges when developing phenotypes are:

- a) *Ensuring portability to other healthcare settings and eras.* Phenotypes can become out of date as coding practices change and new codes are introduced, and may not be easily translatable to other ontologies or healthcare systems.
- b) *Balancing sensitivity and specificity.* We need to balance how confident we are that we are capturing all patients with the relevant feature, against how confident we are that all patients we identify as having that feature did in fact have the feature.

The three main approaches to developing phenotyping algorithms are:

1. **Deterministic approaches**, whereby clinicians identify relevant codes, strings of free text, pharmaceutical prescriptions, or clinical measurements that they would expect to be used to indicate a diagnosis or other feature of interest. These are then combined using a series of logical steps to form a deterministic algorithm which will produce the same result (often a binary flag for

disease status) every time it is executed on the same dataset. Coding systems with a hierarchical structure, such as Read codes or SNOMED CT (Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms), can also be leveraged to identify relevant sibling or parent codes.⁹ This could give a code list portability outside of its current use by practitioners in a given healthcare system. Although time consuming, these approaches are well-established, with step-by-step guidelines available.¹⁰ However, they also rely on expertise from clinicians who know the full range of ways that information can be recorded in practice.

2. Data-led approaches encompass several probabilistic phenotyping methods. One method would be to find patients known, from other sources (such as a national registry or directly from patient notes), to have the feature of interest and to examine how this has been recorded in electronic health records, either in coded data or using natural language processing.¹¹ More broadly, data-led approaches include methods based on clustering of commonly occurring codes or of patterns of healthcare use^{12,13}. These methods are inherently non-deterministic, and tailored to the dataset in which they are developed. The advantage is they can capture patients with a feature of interest that may be missed using a single code list generated by a handful of clinical advisors, and so maximise sensitivity. However, they identify codes used in a particular time and place, and may lack portability to other settings.

3. Hybrid, combined approaches include both deterministic and probabilistic methods. We recommend this approach. First, clinical review is vital for improving the specificity of data-generated phenotyping algorithms. For example, a surgical resection code list was generated by identifying the most common procedures occurring shortly after cancer diagnosis, which were then reviewed for specificity by clinicians, who excluded irrelevant procedures.⁸ Secondly, researchers can use data-led approaches to ‘enhance’ the sensitivity of existing code lists. This could include code lists generated through deterministic approaches (1), but also pre-existing lists translated from another ontology using Common Data Models (CDMs). One example of a CDM is the Observational and Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP), an open community aiming to standardise the structure and terminology of observational data across different clinical settings and geographies, using standardised vocabulary curated by the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) community (<https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization>).

Whichever approach is used to develop the phenotype used to identify clinical features, it will never identify patients with the relevant feature with 100% accuracy. This is particularly pertinent when researchers lack access to free text, as this inevitably leads to misclassification of some patients as being free of a disease or symptom. Validating the accuracy of the electronic health record-based phenotype is essential and involves internal validation, including verification using other patient characteristics (e.g. males should not have endometriosis) and searching for variation in recording over time and between organisations; and external validation, including comparing the recording with published vital statistics, government surveillance, and registries.

In addition to considering the sensitivity of a phenotyping algorithm, the meaning of specific phenotypes also needs to be considered, as different components of a phenotypic definition may represent different levels of disease or symptom severity. The current research funding environment, which is focussed on delivering specific projects, inevitably results in researchers deprioritising the thorough validation phenotypes and sharing them according to FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reuse (see <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>); increased funding is needed for data infrastructure development that could support a range of research.

Mitigating selective recording of clinical features

Beyond challenges associated with phenotyping, we need to be aware of the process of recording clinical features in electronic health records, and try to mitigate potential related biases. There are two different expressions of this problem.

The first problem relates to the clinical setting. Some diseases may be diagnosed and treated primarily in primary care; for others, diagnosis and management typically happens in secondary care. For example, while we know that primary care records identify most cancer diagnoses, a substantial proportion of cases are only recorded in hospital data or the cancer registry.¹⁴ In diagnostic research, we may care about investigations, but when working only with primary care data we will often miss investigations carried out in secondary care, as secondary care data is rarely systematically fed back to primary care. Using linked data from multiple data sources can help to capture all relevant events but may be impractical (e.g. due to data governance restrictions). Where data linkages are possible, we must decide which data sources to prioritise or discount in case of disagreement. For example, we must decide whether we accept a primary care record of cancer without a matching diagnosis in the cancer registry, or how to assign the diagnosis date if it varies across datasets.¹⁴

The second problem relates to whether information is recorded at all, in any accessible dataset. For example, in studies of cancer risk in patients with potential symptoms, we know there is a sequence of multiple steps that are necessary for a patient's symptom to be recorded (Figure 1). The patient must present to a healthcare provider; they must report the symptom; the physician must appreciate that the patient has reported the symptom; and they must choose to include this symptom in the consultation record in a way that researchers can access^{15,16}.

Since the information available to researchers relies on its reporting by patients and recording by clinicians, we can expect this to vary between healthcare providers, between patient groups, and between years. Temporal variation can be pronounced, as with the recording of smoking status in primary care in the UK following the introduction of a related financial incentive in 2004.¹⁷ Coding accuracy may also be affected by the person responsible for coding; in UK primary care this is typically the primary care physician, while in UK secondary care this is often a 'clinical coder' who does not have medical qualifications.

Clinical features are known to be selectively recorded by primary care physicians as coded data (as opposed to free text). We know that symptoms mentioned in free-text notes are coded more often in patients who are later diagnosed with cancer than those who are not (Figure 1).¹⁸ Such selective recording may bias risk estimates, if only coded data is available to researchers, as is often the case in UK research. At minimum, studies should discuss the implications of this completeness problem, though there are currently no established solutions. Data are strongly missing not at random and standard statistical approaches to handling missing data are impractical due to the large-scale longitudinal nature of the datasets; it would not be practical to impute symptom status on every single day over a 10-year study period. We can try to triangulate against other relevant information, for example confirming the degree of weight loss captured in GP coded data using weight and height measurements.¹⁹ We can also examine recording trends over time and by healthcare provider, to try to ensure we are capturing a consistent feature across the entire dataset. Methodological research

in this subject is needed; ideally where free text records are made available to researchers to establish the mechanisms behind non-random missingness.

Dealing with censoring and competing risks

As we follow up patients in longitudinal electronic health records to identify relevant outcome events, we frequently encounter issues caused by losing patients from follow-up. Issues can result from either not being able to observe a diagnosis of interest that did in fact occur, for example if the patient leaves the healthcare provider (see Figure 2, patient 4), or – for competing events such as death – the patient being prevented from experiencing a diagnosis of interest (Figure 2, patient 3). Key concepts are explained in Box 2.

In prognostic research, where researchers are usually interested in diagnosis of a disease many years after entry to the cohort, administrative censoring or censoring due to death is often a major problem. But in diagnostic research we are interested in the risk of present but as-yet-undiagnosed disease, and so we typically follow up patients for just one or two years after entry, meaning that only a small proportion of patients are lost to follow-up and therefore censored.

We should still assess the scale of censoring by looking at the proportion of patients who died or de-registered with their healthcare provider, or - if available from the database provider - by seeing for how long patients continue to have recorded contacts with their healthcare provider after their entry to the cohort. Often only a low percent of patients have de-registered from the healthcare provider or died, and so loss-to-follow-up may be ignorable. Additionally, administrative loss-to-follow-up can be mitigated if we can reliably continue follow up in another linked population-level dataset, although this can introduce other forms of bias (see below).

Ignoring censoring allows us to summarise the risk of underlying-but-undetected disease as the proportion of all patients in the cohort who develop the disease by the end of the follow-up period, regardless of whether any of those patients died or were lost to follow-up. Various diagnostic research studies take this approach,²⁰⁻²² rather than adopting time-to-event approaches such as Cox proportional-hazards models. The problem with simple time-to-event models is that their coefficients (i.e. hazard ratios) do not give us information that can inform guideline recommendations about the actual risk in patients with a presenting feature of interest, and how this differs to their baseline risk.²³ Assuming there is minimal loss-to-follow-up, the simplest way to estimate actual risk is to use proportions and, perhaps, to model it and produce predicted proportions using logistic, Poisson or negative binomial regression.^{21,24} We recommend that when using this approach, the time horizon used is reported (e.g. 12 months after follow up start), to ensure risk estimates can be compared to other studies.

Nevertheless, if the degree of loss-to-follow-up is substantial or cannot be quantified, then simple proportions and related modelling approaches could become unacceptably biased. This is particularly important when aiming to assess the risk of an undetected disease of interest (e.g. cancer) in elderly patients, as typically non-ignorable proportions of these patients die even during short-term follow-up. Disease risk may be low in these patients because they do not survive long enough to be diagnosed with the disease of interest.

In such cases, researchers may have to adopt time-to-event approaches – though we are still interested in estimating the actual proportions of patients in whom a relevant diagnosis can be observed. Coefficients from a naïve proportional-hazards model may not be sufficient, as they relate to a hypothetical world in which patients do not die. To overcome this, we can use time-to-event approaches to model cumulative incidence directly, for example using Fine-Gray models²⁴ or by directly modelling the occurrence of competing events as well as the outcome of interest.

Conceptual challenges in cohort study design for diagnostic research

In addition to practical challenges in using electronic health records datasets in diagnostic research, conceptual challenges also apply specifically to using electronic health records to design cohorts of patients with one or more features of interest. Such conceptual challenges primarily arise from the difficulty of identifying exposures and selecting index dates in large-scale longitudinal data where completeness of recording may be in doubt. Solutions depend on the precise aim of the diagnostic research.

Categorising exposure status when under-recording is suspected

When working with selectively recorded data items from electronic health records, we will typically assume that those marked as having the exposure are indeed exposed. This does not apply fully to all types of exposures; for instance, some disease records could represent initial misdiagnoses; but it seems a safe assumption to make for symptoms and measurements. For example, In UK primary care data, patients with a recorded consultation for jaundice almost certainly would have had jaundice at that time. But we know that not all symptom presentations are coded, and so some fraction of patients who do not have a recorded jaundice will in fact have consulted for jaundice (Figure 1).¹⁵

When solely aiming to develop a risk prediction model, in theory we may be able to ignore under-recording, if recording habits remain stable. Models intended for integration into an electronic health record system will work from the coded data, so the biases in the development data will broadly match the biases in the data fed into the model in practice. Our model will have face validity, if integrated into the same electronic health record system. However, in practice, recording practices are likely to change, particularly since the implementation of a risk prediction model could draw clinicians' attention to which risk factors are important to record, thereby increasing their recording and changing their predictive value. In addition, risk estimates may not be portable to other electronic health record systems or geographic areas.

If instead we are interested in describing the true excess risk of a disease associated with a (potentially) selectively recorded exposure, we must consider the mechanisms leading to under-recording, and the implications of such mechanisms for identifying appropriate comparator groups to calculate 'excess risk'.

Choosing comparator groups to estimate excess risk associated with an exposure

When our research aim is to estimate the true excess risk of a disease associated with a potential prodromal feature, we have two questions to answer when choosing a comparator group:

First, should the exposed group be compared to matched patients 'without-recorded-exposure' or to the wider population of patients? Comparisons have been made to patients 'without-recorded exposure' using case-control matching and adjustment for confounding.²² However, if under-

recording occurs, the 'no-recorded-exposure' group will contain some patients with the exposure. In contrast, a random sample of the wider population will include patients with the exposure, but its meaning can be understood more intuitively. This echoes the choice facing researchers in studies identifying potential prodromal features of a disease; researchers can use case-control designs, where pre-diagnostic information from patients diagnosed with a disease are compared to undiagnosed patients; or case-cohort designs, where they are compared to a random sample of all people in a population.²⁵

The second question is, if comparing to the wider population, should this be:

1. Patients presenting in the healthcare setting (i.e., those with a consultation, with possible index dates only on dates of actual consultations) (Figure 1, comparator 1);
2. All patients in the healthcare setting whether they consulted or not (comparator 2); or
3. Baseline risk in the general population outside of the healthcare setting (comparator 3)?

A comparison against only patients presenting in primary care mimics the average patient a practitioner might see, but disease risk is already likely to already be elevated in these patients.²⁶ However, this comparison might better estimate the excess risk conferred by presenting specifically with the exposure of interest.

There is no single correct answer to these questions. Decisions must be based on the research questions and recording completeness of the clinical features of interest. In general, and especially where we are interested in multiple different exposures, we suggest that comparing patients with a recorded clinical feature against the entire cohort (Figure 1, comparator 2) will tend to give more interpretable results. There are exceptions. For example, if researching the association between abnormal blood test results and disease risk, we already expect that patients may be selected by their GP to have the blood test because they appeared sicker, so explanatory power could be improved by comparing patients with abnormal results to patients who received the test but did not have abnormal results.

Selecting index exposure dates in large-scale longitudinal datasets

In prospective cohort studies, we enrol patients, measure patient information at baseline examination, and follow them up over time, using the baseline examination date as the obvious index date for start of follow-up. However, when working retrospectively with electronic health records, the baseline date is not obvious, as information on health status and outcomes accumulates through healthcare encounters occurring during a patient's life-course. Therefore, to define electronic health record cohorts we need to select appropriate index dates, typically defining covariates as events recorded on or before this date, and outcomes as events that were recorded afterwards.

The most similar approach to a traditional prospective cohort study would be to pick a date in time to be the index and follow up all patients from that calendar date (Figure 3, approach 1). But if we are interested in sporadically occurring exposures – for example, possible prodromal symptoms of cancer – we are potentially discarding relevant information on patients who presented with the symptom of interest a few years before or after a chosen calendar date. In Figure 3, approach 1, a

patient could present with fatigue many times during their lifetime but might not have a fatigue record in the short time following the calendar date used as the index date. Such a patient would be missed from the study. To avoid this problem, researchers working with sporadic features typically choose each patient's first or random record of the exposure of interest as the index date, which we term the 'single index date' approach (Figure 3, approach 2).^{3,27,26} Researchers should test the impact of the approach they use to choose the index date. Although its meaning is intuitive, choosing the 'first' ever record of an exposure could potentially bias the sample towards younger patients, which could underestimate the risk of some diseases such as cancer.

While the 'single index date' approach is reasonable when only one exposure is examined, it becomes impractical if we consider multiple exposures (e.g. different symptoms), particularly if controls are defined as patients who were not exposed to any of the features of interest. If examining a range of common symptoms (e.g. fatigue, cough) then the unexposed group will comprise highly selected - and likely inherently healthier - patients.

The 'single index date' approach also presents challenges when trying to identify multiple exposures occurring concurrently in electronic health records. Typically, in this approach, researchers look back before the index presentation with the primary symptom of interest and create a binary flag indicating whether the patient had other symptoms recorded beforehand. But electronic health records cannot tell us definitively when patients started or stopped experiencing a particular transient feature such as a symptom or biomarker. Consider the example of a patient with fatigue, and a possible other symptom, such as cough. We must decide whether a cough recorded three, six, or twelve months before a patient's index fatigue record should mean the patient is flagged as having it when they present with fatigue, and whether both symptoms could relate to the same (as-yet undetected) disease. Similar questions apply to comorbidities that might confer increased risk of the disease outcome of interest. For instance, it could be assumed that patients diagnosed many years ago with a chronic illness such as type 1 diabetes still have it, whereas those with tuberculosis may not. We recommend seeking clinical advice about the stages of disease development and persistence, and the maximum length of the 'prodromal' period during which symptoms and related diagnoses may occur.

Data recording in electronic health records can also have lags, due to delays in either patients reporting or practitioners entering information. So, when using the 'single index date' approach, we may wish to include some time *after* an index date to search for co-occurring exposures - accepting the resulting immortal time bias (Supplementary material).²⁸ Finally, by selecting a time period around a single index presentation, we end up ignoring potentially valuable data again. While many patients may present to healthcare services with concurrent cough and fatigue at some point in their lives, the chances of this occurring within the short window around a particular index date for fatigue is lower.

Dynamic approaches to analysis are appealing when there is no clear, single, index date. Many such approaches are possible, including landmarking (with one variant illustrated in Figure 3, approach 3),²⁹ multi-state modelling,³⁰ and joint longitudinal-survival models,³¹ and the appropriate approaches will inevitably depend on the exact research question. In general, dynamic modelling is an appealing way to taking advantage of the longitudinal nature of electronic health records, and combining multiple exposures of interest - both stable (e.g. age, sex) and transient (e.g. symptoms and test results). Handling these two types of predictors in such models is challenging, as transient predictors may be strongly associated with risk in the short-term but not in the medium to long-term.

Designing study cohorts to answer the correct research question

There is no one-size-fits-all solution to using electronic health records for diagnostic research studies: the way we design study cohorts and structure analysis datasets should be guided by our research question. In Table 1, we present examples of possible observational cohort designs and which diagnostic research questions they are best suited to answer.

Drawing on the PROGRESS framework for prognostic research, we propose three distinct types of diagnostic research studies using cohorts derived from electronic health records:

1. Overall diagnosis research. Studies that summarise the average short-term risk of present but as-yet undetected disease (e.g., cancer) among people presenting in a healthcare setting with the sign or symptom of interest.
2. Diagnostic factor research. Studies that identify factors whose values are associated with changes in short-term risk of present but as-yet undetected disease.
3. Diagnostic model research. Studies that develop, validate or assess the impact of a diagnostic model to predict an individual's short-term risk of present but as-yet undetected disease using combinations of (shorter term) diagnostic and (longer term) prognostic factors.

Some studies address multiple research questions, often for good reason. Much diagnostic research aims to summarise the *actual* short-term risk of a disease in a group of patients with a specific clinical feature (e.g. symptom or blood test result). This is crucial to inform guideline recommendations to identify patient groups whose risk exceeds a specific threshold, but it is not informative enough in isolation. We should also care about whether patients with that feature have notably higher risk than those without that feature, since baseline disease risk in some patient groups may already be high. For example, cancer risk in older men exceeds the UK referral thresholds without considering clinical features.²¹ And so, most overall diagnosis research is also diagnostic factor research, with both absolute risk and excess risk being of clinical interest.

Diagnostic model and diagnostic factor research also overlap. Some diagnostic value studies build models to assess which of multiple exposures are most strongly associated with disease risk.³² However, as with prognostic model research, conclusions from data-driven multivariable models about which exposures have diagnostic value requires consideration of possible causal relationships between covariates, to avoid the 'table 2 fallacy'.^{33 34}

Finally, diagnostic models could be used to answer overall diagnosis research questions, by using model coefficients to generate predicted cumulative probabilities for groups of patients with a specific clinical feature. Only a handful of use cases exist; for example, the Qcancer models have informed UK urgent referral guidelines for suspected cancer.^{3,29} Coefficients from these models (i.e. proportional hazards) should be used with caution, as they apply to a hypothetical context in which patients do not die from other causes, and could overestimate disease risk in patients at high risk of death.³⁵ This must either be communicated in their interpretation, or alternative methods used to model cumulative incidence. In general, if models are made publicly available, thought is needed around how to communicate risk, particularly as the risk estimates are based on primary care data, so will likely overestimate disease risk in people experiencing the same symptoms in the community (Figure 1).

Conclusions

We provide reflections and recommendations (summarised in Box 3) on using electronic health record datasets to conduct diagnostic research into short-term risk of present but as-yet undetected disease in patients with potential prodromal features. This growing research area continues to help doctors make decisions about which diagnoses to suspect in presenting patients, and has led to the proliferation of risk prediction tools, a minority of which are already used in practice.

We provide recommendations for overcoming practical challenges in these studies arising directly from the nature of electronic health records, which can often be straightforwardly addressed. More discussion is needed around conceptual challenges in designing cohorts with prodromal features. We recommend that researchers explore the sensitivity of study conclusions to decisions such as the choice of index date, and precisely communicate the clinical meaning of exposure and comparison groups to clinicians and policy makers.

There is little guidance addressing the use of electronic health records to design cohorts for diagnostic research, but for further reading, we direct readers the points on opportunity for information recording raised by Williams,³⁶ and the various pitfalls highlighted by Sauer and colleagues that are of most relevance for risk modelling using machine learning.³⁷ Reporting guidelines including STROBE,³⁸ RECORD⁵, TRIPOD,⁶ CODE-EHR,³⁹ and Matthewman et al⁴⁰ also offer hints to important issues in study design. We also recommend a broader discussion of other common biases in observational research not covered in this article, by Grimes and Schulz.⁴¹

Above, all, because having a clear research question is critical to guiding researchers' conceptual decisions, we recommend considering where studies can be situated within the broader framework of diagnostic research.

Contributors

BW, MB, and GL conceived and designed this article. All authors contributed to drafting and revising the article. BW is the guarantor. The corresponding author attests that all listed authors meet authorship criteria and that no others meeting the criteria have been omitted.

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Patients and the public were not directly involved in the drafting of this guidance.

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Box 1. Strengths and limitations of using electronic health records in research.

Strengths

- *Coverage.* Many databases cover large populations spanning whole regions, allowing examination of rare diseases or specific patient strata.
- *Representativeness.* Data is collected through routine care, and consent often operates on an opt-out basis, helping reduce selection bias and the 'healthy volunteer' effect.
- *Patient follow-up.* Provided movement of patients and healthcare providers between database systems is minimal, patients have many years of continuous follow up.
- *Data richness.* Data is longitudinal and can be used to build up a dynamic picture of patients' changing health over their lives, often including demographic information, consultations, symptoms and diagnoses, tests, prescriptions, and referrals to other services
- *Data linkage.* Many database providers offer routine patient-level linkage to other datasets, such as disease registers, other primary or secondary care datasets, and area-level data e.g. deprivation.

Limitations

- *Censoring and follow up.* In non-national electronic health record databases (e.g. UK primary care), there are additional ways that patients are 'lost to follow-up':
 - Patients cannot easily be traced if they change healthcare providers, or move to a provider that uses another software system.
 - A healthcare provider may change database software providers, which interrupts follow up for all its patients.
- *Identifying outcomes and exposures.* Data can be overly granular and 'messy', so phenotypes need to be created to identify diseases and their features.
- *Selective recording of clinical features.* Free text and imaging data is not typically available to researchers. Recording of features (e.g. symptoms) is influenced by patient behaviour, practitioner training and perception of the patient's underlying disease risk, and financial incentive schemes.
- *Sporadic observations.* Since patients' health statuses are only recorded when they present to healthcare providers, it is difficult to know exactly when their health changed (e.g. when symptoms start and end).
- *Generalisability to the general population.* Signs and symptoms experienced in the community are not necessarily reported by patients, so findings relate only to patients who present them to healthcare services.
- *Generalisability to other health systems.* Associations between diseases and potential features may not be generalisable to other healthcare systems with different recording practices, service organisation or clinical practice guidelines.

Figure 1. Theoretical 'symptom iceberg' in patients presenting to healthcare services and its implications for selecting comparison cohorts.

Box 2. Key concepts relating to censoring

Loss-to-follow-up

When we lose track of a patient – which in a study using linked data may affect some but not all of our data sources. This typically includes death or leaving the electronic health record database (either by changing healthcare provider or their healthcare provider changing database software).

Competing events

Events that mean it is impossible for a patient to experience the primary outcome of concern, typically but not necessarily death (for instance, for a study of endometrial cancer risk, hysterectomy would be a competing event).

Index date

The date that follow-up begins for a patient. This can be identified in many ways, including calendar date, patient age, or a recorded event e.g. symptom.

Censoring

The date at which we stop following-up a patient for their study-related outcomes, which will often be either the end of the study period (e.g., 12 months after their index date) or when they have their first outcome event. Loss-to-follow-up and competing events may both lead to early censoring, although may need different handling in the analysis.

Figure 2. Illustration of patient 'loss to follow up'

Figure 3. Illustration of approaches to selecting exposure dates

Table 1. Examples of observational cohort designs and their applications in diagnostic research

Study design	Description	Examples	Diagnostic research question
1) Single cohort design with no comparison	Disease risk is described in a cohort of patients presenting with a sign / symptom. Risk estimates can be stratified by patient characteristics and other presenting features, such as symptoms, test results, previous diagnoses, etc.	Risk of 35 non-malignant diagnoses in patients presenting in primary care with abdominal pain ⁴²	Overall diagnosis
2) Single cohort with comparison			
a) Reference population	Disease risk in the cohort with a sign / symptom is compared to that of a reference comparator group external to the studied population (e.g. the general population, or primary care presenters without the symptom), which is usually case-mix adjusted to the cohort based on age and sex. ²¹	Cancer risk in patients presenting in primary care with fatigue compared to the general population in England, adjusting for age and sex ²⁷	Overall diagnosis Diagnostic factor
b) Matched controls	Disease risk in the cohort with a sign / symptom is compared to that of primary care-based controls, who are selected by matching on age, sex, presentation during a similar period, and sometimes GP practice. ⁴³ Controls could include randomly selected patients who: i. are registered to a GP (regardless of whether they presented in primary care) ii. presented in primary care (regardless of the sign/ symptom) iii. presented without the sign / symptom of interest	Cancer risk in patients presenting in primary care with unexpected weight loss compared to patients presenting without ⁴³	
3) Open cohort			
a) With single baseline	All registered patients are followed up for a time period following an index date (often a random date or date of entry to the database followed by a 'washout' period). Their sign/ symptom status is identified using a lookback period before (or sometimes after) the index date, and disease risk compared in patients with and without the sign / symptom at baseline (adjusting for other exposures). ³	Estimating cancer risk in women in primary care, based on patient characteristics, family history, comorbidities, symptoms ³	Overall diagnosis Diagnostic factor Diagnostic model
b) With multiple baselines (Landmark)	All registered patients are followed up for a time period following a landmark date e.g. landmark age. The same patient can be included multiple times (with appropriate handling of standard errors), with each cohort modelled separately, or combined into one model. ²⁹	Estimating colorectal cancer risk in patients in primary care, based on patient characteristics, genetic information, lifestyle factors, test results, symptoms ²⁹	
c) Other dynamic approaches	More complex designs are available that continuously model how patients' health states change over time (e.g. joint modelling, multistate modelling). ^{30,44} Data preparation needs for these studies are very specific and not covered in this article.	Estimating pancreatic cancer risk in patients following progression of pancreatitis. ⁴⁵	

Box 3. Summary recommendations

Practical challenges in processing electronic health records data

Identifying outcomes and exposures

- Try to make phenotypes portable, sensitive, and specific enough for your needs.
- Consider hybrid approaches to phenotyping, combining deterministic and probabilistic approaches.

Mitigating selective recording of clinical features

- Maximise the capture of under-recorded data items by combining linked datasets.
- If not possible to address by design, report the anticipated scale of under-recording, and whether it is Missing Not At Random (MNAR).

Dealing with censoring and competing risks

- Ascertain the scale of censoring (loss to follow up and death).
- Decide whether your research aims need a result that applies to a real-world population (e.g., cumulative risk study), or a hypothetical population where competing events do not exist.
- Clearly report the follow-up time used to calculate cumulative risk.

Conceptual challenges in cohort study design for diagnostic research

Categorising exposure status when under-recording is suspected

- When interpreting results, consider that 'exposure-free' comparator groups may include patients who did indeed have the exposure.
- Under-recording of an exposure can sometimes be ignored in risk prediction models, but the resulting models are likely only valid in settings with similar coding practices.

Choosing comparator groups to estimate excess risk associated with an exposure

- When under-recording of an exposure is suspected, comparisons between exposed / unexposed patients can become biased and difficult to interpret.
- Consider comparing risk in exposed patients to 'baseline risk' in a cohort of all patients (both those with / without the exposure), especially if interested in multiple different exposures.

Selecting index exposure dates in large-scale longitudinal datasets

- When there is no clear, single, index date, consider dynamic approaches where multiple index dates can be included per patient.
- Seek clinical advice about the timing of disease development and associated symptoms.
- Beware of immortal time bias caused by defining cohorts based on the recording of features after the start of follow up.

Designing study cohorts to answer the correct research question

- To guide all decisions about cohort design, decide whether the study is primarily 1. Overall diagnosis research, 2. Diagnostic factor research, or 3. Diagnostic model research.

Supplementary material. Demonstration of immortal time bias caused by including post-index exposures

Immortal time bias is a type of bias where it is impossible for an outcome of interest to occur for a period of time during follow up, because of the way an exposure was defined. The simulation in Stata below demonstrates how including post-index exposures can induce immortal time bias to electronic health record studies.

Let us consider a (simulated) cohort of 30,000 patients presenting with Symptom A, with their index date being the day on which they present with Symptom A. We follow up these patients for one year, and we will simulate events on each day of that year.

For every patient in the cohort, when date = 0, this represents the index date, or the day the patient presented with Symptom A.

```
/* Briefly simulate data */
clear

* set seed
set seed 1157

* 100k patients
set obs 30000
gen id = _n

* 1 year follow-up.
expand 365
bys id: gen date = _n
```

We will consider a second symptom, 'Symptom B', and how this affects risk of cancer. We will simulate a 1/200 risk of consulting for 'Symptom B' on each day of follow-up.

For every patient, we will simulate a 1/1000 risk of developing cancer on each day of follow-up. There is no true association between 'Symptom B' and risk of cancer, so this will not be affected by the presence of 'Symptom B'.

- * on any given day, 1/1000 chance of developing cancer
- * on any given day, 1/200 chance of consulting for a symptom
- * no true relationship between cancer and symptom

```
gen cancer = rbinomial(1,.001)
gen symptom_b = rbinomial(1,0.005)
```

```
tab symptom_b
```

* symptom_b	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
*-----+-----			
* 0	10,894,986	99.50	99.50
* 1	55,014	0.50	100.00
*-----+-----			
* Total	10,950,000	100.00	

```
tab cancer
```

* cancer	Freq.	Percent	Cum.
*-----+-----			
* 0	10,939,006	99.90	99.90
* 1	10,994	0.10	100.00
*-----+-----			
* Total	10,950,000	100.00	

We will identify the first date on which each patient presents with 'Symptom B', and the first date on which they have a cancer diagnosis, during follow-up. We can see that around a third of patients develop cancer and most present with 'Symptom B' at some point during follow-up.

```
* identify date of first symptom / first cancer
gen symptom_b_date = date*symptom_b if symptom_b != 0
gen cancer_date = date*cancer if cancer != 0
```

```
collapse (min) symptom_b_date cancer_date, by(id)
list in 1/10
```

```
*
* +-----+
* | id  sympto~e  cancer~e |
* +-----+
* 1. | 1      122      . |
* 2. | 2      .      93 |
* 3. | 3      58      . |
* 4. | 4      210     158 |
* 5. | 5      .      . |
* +-----+
* 6. | 6      76      . |
* 7. | 7      255     . |
* 8. | 8      289     . |
* 9. | 9      164     . |
* 10. | 10     .      . |
* +-----+
```

```
* flag for whether patients had cancer within 365 days of entry
gen byte cancer = !missing(cancer_date)
tab cancer
```

```
*
* cancer |      Freq.      Percent      Cum.
* +-----+
*      0 |      20,775      69.25      69.25
*      1 |       9,225      30.75     100.00
* +-----+
*      Total |      30,000     100.00
```

```
* flag for whether patients had symptom within 365 days of entry
gen byte symptom_b = !missing(symptom_b_date)
tab symptom_b
```

```
*
* symptom_b |      Freq.      Percent      Cum.
* +-----+
*      0 |       4,764      15.88      15.88
*      1 |      25,236      84.12     100.00
* +-----+
*      Total |      30,000     100.00
```

Typically, in diagnostic research, researchers:

- Ignore exposures that occur after a diagnosis (so no symptoms after a patient is diagnosed with cancer)
- Limit to additional symptoms that occur within one or three months of diagnosis

Thus we create flags for presentation with symptom B within 30 and 90 days *after* the index date, but before cancer diagnosis.

```
* flag for whether patients had symptom within 30 days after the
index date, and before cancer
gen byte symptom_b_30 = (symptom_b_date <= 30) & (symptom_b_date <
cancer_date)
tab symptom_b_30
```

```
*symptom_b_3 |
*      0 |      Freq.      Percent      Cum.
*-----+-----
*      0 |      25,898      86.33      86.33
*      1 |       4,102      13.67      100.00
*-----+-----
*      Total |      30,000      100.00
```

```
* flag for whether patients had symptom within 90 days after the
index date, and before cancer
gen byte symptom_b_90 = (symptom_b_date <= 90) & (symptom_b_date <
cancer_date)
tab symptom_b_90
```

```
*symptom_b_9 |
*      0 |      Freq.      Percent      Cum.
*-----+-----
*      0 |      19,555      65.18      65.18
*      1 |      10,445      34.82      100.00
*-----+-----
*      Total |      30,000      100.00
```

By design, there is no real association between symptom B and risk of cancer.

But if we consider the observed data based on these 30 and 90 day flags, we see that cancer risk is lower in patients without symptom B, when using these definitions:

```
* Describe cancer risk by 30-day flag
```

```
local cell_formats nototals nformat(%9.0f freq) nformat(%4.1f  
fvpercent) `sformat("%s%" fvpercent)
```

```
table (symptom_b_30) (), statistic(freq) statistic(fvpercent cancer)  
`cell_formats'
```

```
*-----  
*          | Frequency   Factor-variable percent  
*          |          cancer  
*          |          0          1  
*-----+-----  
*symptom_b_30 |  
* 0          |      25898      69.0%      31.0%  
* 1          |      4102      70.6%      29.4%  
*-----+-----
```

```
logit cancer i.symptom_b_30, or cformat(%3.2f)
```

```
*-----+-----  
*          cancer | Odds ratio   Std. err.      z    P>|z|      [95% conf. interval]  
*-----+-----  
*1.symptom_b_30 |          0.93   0.03    -2.02   0.044      0.86      1.00  
*          _cons |          0.45   0.01   -59.66   0.000      0.44      0.46  
*-----+-----
```

```
* Describe cancer risk by 90-day flag
```

```
table (symptom_b_90) (), statistic(freq) statistic(fvpercent cancer)  
`cell_formats'
```

```
*-----+-----  
*          | Frequency   Factor-variable percent  
*          |          cancer  
*          |          0          1  
*-----+-----  
*symptom_b_90 |  
* 0          |     19555     67.6%     32.4%  
* 1          |     10445     72.3%     27.7%  
*-----+-----
```

```
logit cancer i.symptom_b_30, or cformat(%3.2f)
```

```
*-----+-----  
*          cancer | Odds ratio   Std. err.      z    P>|z|      [95% conf. interval]  
*-----+-----  
*1.symptom_b_90 |          0.80   0.02   -8.34   0.000      0.76      0.84  
*          _cons |          0.48   0.01  -48.20   0.000      0.46      0.49  
*-----+-----
```

That is, patients presenting with Symptom B appear to be at lower risk of cancer than those who do not, and the difference is more pronounced when we use a 90-day window rather than a 30-day window.

This is not surprising: it is a classical example of immortal time bias.

We have defined symptom B by specifying that it has to be recorded after the index date but before a cancer diagnosis, so there is some period of time in their follow up after the index date in which case they are, by definition, unable to have a cancer diagnosis. This same criteria does not apply to the 'exposure-free' group of patients without symptom B.

So this protective effect is completely driven by the design demonstrated here.

This kind of issue is common in research with electronic health records data, and researchers need to be careful when identifying exposures to mitigate the risk of immortal time bias. Because of the way data is generated, we often want to allow some post-index window for identifying exposures, because symptoms or diseases may be present and known at index but may not immediately be recorded.

However, it is vital that any post-index window, if truly necessary, is as short as possible, to avoid serious potential problems caused by immortal time bias. Issues may often be more pronounced than shown here, as typically risk of a diagnosis is highest in the first few days and weeks following presentation with a relevant feature.

Note on environment:

- *StataNow/MP 18.5 for Windows (64-bit x86-64)*
- *Revision 04 Sep 2024*
- *Copyright 1985-2023 StataCorp LLC*